

**INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY AND LEARNING
TECHNIQUES IN POST COVID-19 ERA: CASE STUDY OF BABCOCK UNIVERSITY
STUDENTS**

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ABSTRACT

This study's aim was to investigate the effect of ICT on learning activities among students of Babcock University, Ilishan Remo, Ogun State in post COVID-19 era. Two research questions and one null hypothesis were formulated for the study.

The survey research method was used and a self-structured questionnaire which was administered to students in Babcock University served as the instrument. The population for the study consisted of 11,000 Babcock University students out of which 386 were picked as sample using stratified random sampling. The research questions were analyzed using descriptive statistics while the hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance using multiple regression analysis.

It was revealed from the findings that the major learning techniques obtainable in Babcock University is taking down notes for future reading (\bar{x} = 3.42; St.D = .87). The students also prefer to see information written on the board, supplemented by assigned readings and visual aids (\bar{x} = 3.34; St.D = .85). They tend to remember things best when they write it down several times. The most available ICT tool being used in Babcock is Google Classroom (\bar{x} = 3.72; St.D = .67) and this is closely followed by Google Meet (\bar{x} = 3.34; St.D = .94). The result revealed a significant positive relationship between ICT tools used and learning techniques in Babcock University (r = .411, $P < 0.05$).

This study concluded that there is a positive relationship between ICT and learning techniques. Based on the finding of this study, it was recommended that current ICT tools can aid learning techniques.

Keywords: Information, Communication, Technology, Learning Techniques, Covid-19.

Introduction

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is a group of technological tools and resources that are used to share, transmit, store, create, or exchange information. These technological tools and resources include computers, the internet (websites, blogs and emails), live broadcasting technologies (television, radio and webcasting), recorded broadcasting technologies (audio and video players, podcasting, and storage devices) and telephony (fixed or mobile, satellite, visio/video-conferencing, etc.) (Ibenwa *et al.*, 2024).

The COVID-19 pandemic has forced educators and students at all levels of education to immediately adapt to online learning which involves the use of ICT tools. The impact of this and the developments required to make it work could permanently change how education is delivered.

The COVID-19 pandemic also forced the world to accept and adopt the current use of ICT in learning. Although online and distance learning has been used before to maintain continuity in education, such as in the aftermath of earthquakes (Mackay *et al.*, 2012), the scale of the current crisis is unprecedented. Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, many people and educational organizations see online education as an alternative pathway to the traditional mode of learning (Hodges, 2020), but now, online education is becoming the go to mode for both teaching and learning. The lockdown brought about a paradigm shift from the physical learning strategies to the online mode (Murphy, 2020). During the lockdown, schools were not allowed to open and it was difficult for students to learn physically. This made most schools move their operations and teachings online so as to ensure that the students were engaged.

Technology helps both teachers and students to easily access various materials in different formats. It also help save spaces that will usually be taken up by hardcopy materials (Skulmowski, 2020).

As a result of COVID-19, institutions and educational organizations are now having online classes via software such as Microsoft Teams, Google Meet, Zoom, Google Classroom, and so on. In Babcock University, the students are made to offer their General Education Courses (GEDS) online. This is achieved through the use of software platforms like Microsoft Teams, Google Meet and Google Classroom. The techniques used in online learning is a bit different from the physical learning because the students and teacher (s) are not physically in contact with each other. Even in the physical learning, ICT still play important roles in the post COVID-19 era as we now have interactive digital whiteboards replacing the traditional chalkboard. Students are also now allowed to bring in tablets and laptops into classes to give them the technological feeling that they crave for.

Technology in education has brought about a different type of learning technique for students. Because online teaching is technology based, learners have had to readjust themselves to the demands of online education. This entails that the students have gadgets like laptop, smartphones, tablets or desktop. In addition to this is the availability of stable internet connection, this can be gotten by subscribing through a mobile network or connection to a WIFI network.

Online education require students to submit assignments, write quizzes and tests and even take exams online. Most times, the lecturer give assignments or quizzes with a deadline attached to it. This means that the students must be time conscious so as not to be timed out or marked out for late submission. The lecturers also send materials online which the students are required to download and read. These materials may include recorded videos and audios or attachments in form of notes and PowerPoints.

Some lecturers also require students to do presentations on topics either as an individual or as a group. As good as ICT is in education, it also has its downside which may include network lag, lack of seriousness from students part, students not understanding some teachings especially calculations, power outage leading to flat battery on devices and students not having enough data.

Research Questions

- i. Will ICT tools affect learning techniques in post COVID-19 era among Babcock University students?
- ii. What are the various ICT tools used for learning in post COVID-19 era among Babcock University students?

Methodology

This study adopted a survey research design approach. The study population comprised a total of 11,000 students in Babcock University, Ilishan Remo. The research instrument used for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was used for collecting responses from the subject selected for the study which consisted of three sections.

Section A consisted of questions for the demographics. Section B included the ICT scale. The section C focused on learning technique scale.

The likert-scale was used to measure opinions, Strongly Disagree = 4, Disagree = 3, Strongly Agree = 2, Agree = 1. A reliability coefficient of 0.751 was obtained for the questionnaire. The data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics was used to analyze the demographic section while the inferential was used to test the stated hypotheses. All tests were considered significant at the alpha level of 0.05.

Results and Findings

4.1. Demographic Presentation

Table 4.1 Frequency Distribution of Participant's Demographic Data

S/No.	Variable	Category	Frequency (N= 369)	Percentage
	Gender	Male	215	58.3
		Female	154	41.7
	Age	18 - 20 years	154	41.7
		Over 20 years	215	58.3
	Religion	Christianity	241	65.3
		Islam	128	34.7
	Ethnicity	Yoruba	246	66.7
		Igbo	77	20.9
		Hausa	46	12.5

Source: Field Survey 2022

Table 4.1 reveals the respondents demographic distribution. It was indicated that a majority of the respondent were male 215 (58.3%) while 154 (41.7%) were female. The table further revealed that 154 (41.7%) were within the ages of 18-20years while 215 (58.3%) were within the ages of 20 years and above. Hence, most of the respondents were within the ages of 20 years and above. It was also revealed that 241 (65.3%) of the respondents were Christians, while 128 (34.7%) were Muslims. Hence, most of the respondents were Christians. The table also showed that 246 (66.7%) of the respondents were Yoruba, 77 (20.9%) were Igbo, while 46 (12.5%) were Hausa. Thus, most of the respondents were Yoruba.

Research Question One: What are the learning techniques in post COVID-19 era using Babcock University students as case study?

Table 4.2: LEARNING TECHNIQUE SCALE

S/N	QUESTIONS	Mean (\bar{x})	St.D
1	I can remember best by listening to a lecture that includes information, explanations and discussions	3.33	.79741
2	I prefer to see information written on the board and supplemented by visual aids and assigned readings	3.34	.85
3	I like to write things down or take notes for visual review	3.42	.87
4	I prefer to use posters, models, or actual practice and other activities in class.	3.01	.64
5	I require explanations of diagrams, graphs, or visual directions	3.17	.75
6	I enjoy working with my hands or making things	3.13	.88
7	I am skilful with and enjoy developing making graphs and charts	2.33	.69
8	I can tell if sounds match when presented with pairs of sounds	2.79	.82
9	I can remember best by writing things down several times	3.34	.90
10	I can easily understand and follow directions on a map	2.88	.78
11	I do best in academic subjects by listening to lectures and tapes	3.04	.73

12	I learn to spell better by repeating words out loud than by writing the words on paper	2.95	1.02
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Source: Field Survey 2022

Table 4.2 showed the respondents view on the learning techniques in Babcock University. The result was interpreted using the mean values which has a boundary of 2.5 ($1+2+3+4=10/4=2.5$) acceptance. Result shows that on the average the respondents were of the view that they can remember best by listening to a lecture that includes information, explanations and discussions ($\bar{x}=3.33$; $St.D=.80$), it was deduced that the respondents are of the view that they prefer to see information written on the board and supplemented by visual aids and assigned readings ($\bar{x}=3.34$; $St.D=.85$), they are of the opinion that they like to write things down or take notes for visual review ($\bar{x}=3.42$; $St.D=.87$) and they are also of the view that they prefer to use posters, models, or actual practice and other activities in class ($\bar{x}=3.01$; $St.D=.64$), they are the view that they require explanations of diagrams, graphs, or visual directions ($\bar{x}=3.17$; $St.D=.75$), they are of the opinion that they enjoy working with my hands or making things ($\bar{x}=3.13$; $St.D=.88$), they however, disagree that they were skillful with and enjoy developing making graphs and charts ($\bar{x}=2.33$; $St.D=.69$), it could be deduced from the result that the respondents can tell if sounds match when presented with pairs of sounds ($\bar{x}=2.79$; $St.D=.82$), they also can remember best by writing things down several times ($\bar{x}=3.34$; $St.D=.90$), they believe that they can easily understand and follow directions on a map ($\bar{x}=2.88$; $St.D=.78$), and also believe that they do best in academic subjects by listening to lectures and tapes ($\bar{x}=3.04$; $St.D=.73$), the table finally revealed that on the average, the respondents are of the view that they learn to spell better by repeating words out loud than by writing the words on paper ($\bar{x}=2.95$; $St.D=1.02$). it could be deduced from this result that the major learning techniques obtainable in Babcock University is that the respondents take write down notes to subsequently read and the students also prefer see information written on the board and supplemented by visual aids and assigned readings as they can remember best by writing things down several times.

Research Question Two: What are the types of ICT tools used in post COVID-19 era, using Babcock University students as case study?

Table 4.3: The ICT tools available and used for learning in Babcock University

SN	QUESTIONS	Mean	St.D
1	Google Classroom	3.72	.67

2	Google Meet	3.34	.94
4	Microsoft Teams	3.26	.87
7	Social Media (WhatsApp, YouTube, Facebook, Telegram)	3.26	.72
3	Edmodo	2.53	.91
5	Blackboard	2.07	1.08
10	We Transfer	2.04	.79
9	Dropbox	1.99	.91
8	Kahoot	1.66	.63
6	Trello	1.61	.69

Source: Field Survey 2022

Table 4.3 showed the respondents view on the types of the ICT tools available used in Babcock University. The result was also interpreted using the mean values which has a boundary of 2.5 ($1+2+3+4= 10/4 = 2.5$) acceptance. Result shows that on the average based on responses from the respondents, the most available ICT tool use in Babcock is Google Classroom ($\bar{x}= 3.72$; $St.D= .67$) and this is closely followed by Google Meet ($\bar{x}= 3.34$; $St.D= .94$), Microsoft Teams ($\bar{x}= 3.26$; $St.D=.87$), Social Media ($\bar{x}= 3.26$; $St.D= .72$), Edmodo ($\bar{x}= 2.53$; $St.D= .91$), while the least is Trello ($\bar{x}= 1.61$; $St.D= .69$).

Test of Hypotheses

H₀: There is no significant relationship between ICT tools and learning techniques in post COVID-19 era among Babcock University students

Table 4.3: Correlation Matrix on the relationship between ICT tools and learning techniques in post COVID-19 era among Babcock University students

		LEARNING	ICT
LEARNING	Pearson Correlation	1	.411**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	369	369
ICT	Pearson Correlation	.411**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	369	369

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.3 revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between ICT tools use and the leaning techniques in Babcock University ($r= .411$, $P< 0.05$). This invariably implies the ICT tools use determine the leaning techniques adopted by the students in Babcock.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that for Babcock University students, there is a relationship between ICT and learning techniques. It was recommended that Students should be exposed to more ICT tools that can aid their learning techniques and teachers should be obligated to make use of trending ICT tools in their classroom delivery in order to enrich student learning. Parents should provide ICT tools at home in order to foster a home environment that is conducive to meaningful private study and thereby increase the learning of their children.

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